

CONSTRAINTS AND SUGGESTIONS FACED BY KHARIF GREEN CHILLIGROWERS IN AURANGABAD DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract:

The study was conducted in the year 2020–2021 to study the “Constraints and suggestion faced by Green chilli growers in Aurangabad District of Maharashtra.” Aurangabaddistrict comprise of 9 tehsils in which two tehsils namely Sillod and Soygaon were purposively selected. Three villages were selected from each tahsil which is Amthana, Pendgaon and Dharla from Sillod and from Soygaon villages selected were Soygaon, Galwada and Furdapur in which highest area under Chilli cultivation. From each village 15 chilli farmers were selected randomly thus total sample size were 90 farmers. Data were collected by means of personal interview with the help of pre structured schedule.

Constraints during chilli cultivation faced by farmers are lack of knowledge of nursery management, unavailability of inputs at right time, high cost of fertilizer, etc. Farmers suggest that to take demonstrations on nursery management, provide inputs at right time, provide subsidies on fertilizers and pesticides, etc.

Keywords: Constraints, Suggestions, Chilli growers.

Introduction:

Chilli (*Capsicum annum*), is a valuable crops of India. It is grown almost throughout the country. Lots of varieties are grown for condiments, vegetables, sauces, pickles, spices etc. Chilli is also known as ‘hot pepper’ and capsicum (Shimla Mirchi) as ‘bell pepper.’ The Portuguese came with capsicum from Brazil to the India during the year 1584. Chilli is a fruit of the plants ‘capsicum frutescens’ and ‘capsicum annum.’ Chilli comes from the genus ‘capsicum,’ and it is belonging to the family of ‘Solanaceae’. If some varieties of chillies are famous for red colour because of the pigment ‘capsanthin,’ others are known for biting pungency due to the pigment ‘capsaicin.’ India is the only country which is rich in many varieties with different quality factors. Chilli is considered as one of the best spices used in the Kitchen. The paste of chillies acts like as appetizer. Due to presence of Capsaicin compounds, chilli pepper is used in the preparation of ointment; also used in formulation to be used in arthritic pain and sore muscles. Chilli are used as medicine in diarrhoea, pain and sprain, numbness, heart attack, diabetes.

Methodology:

The study was based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through personal interview method from farmers, with the help of well-structured and pretested questionnaire exclusively designed for the study. Data were collected from farmers,

village traders, wholesalers and retailers, about the price spread, labour charges, transportation costs, commission charges, other charges if any and also the price received by them by personal interview method with the help of pretested interview schedule and pertaining for the year 2020-2021. In the study area chilli was sold in Amthana, Ghatnandra and Fardapur market. Hence, Amthana, Ghatnandra and Fardapur market purposively selected because most of the chilli produce from the study area are marketed in that market.

Result and Discussion:**Constraints And Suggestions Of Chilli Growers:****Constraints faced by chilli growers in Production and Marketing**

The result indicated that the constraints during chilli cultivation, out of total 90 farmers

83.33 per cent farmers faced problem of lack of knowledge of nursery management followed by unavailability of inputs at right time i.e. 75.55 per cent, high cost of fertilizer, insecticide and fungicide i.e. 66.66 per cent, high wage rate of labour i.e. 62.22, labour scarcity during harvesting period 57.77. (Table 1).

Constraints in the marketing of chilli faced by cultivators are non-availability of market information i.e. 88.88 per cent followed by high transportation cost i.e. 77.77 per cent, remunerative prices are not received i.e. 72.22 per cent, high price fluctuation i.e. 64.44 per cent and middle man malpractices take place i.e. 44.44.(Table 1).

Table 1. Constraints faced by chilli growers in Production and Marketing of chilli

Sr.no.	Production and Marketing Constraints	N=90	Percent	Rank
Production constraints				
1.	Lack of knowledge of nursery management	75	83.33	I
2.	Unavailability of inputs including fertilizer, insecticides and pesticide at right time	68	75.55	II
3.	High cost of fertilizer, insecticide and fungicide	60	66.66	III
4.	High wage rate of labour	56	62.22	IV
5.	Labour scarcity during harvesting period	52	57.77	V
Marketing constraints				
1.	Non availability of market information	80	88.88	I
2.	High transportation cost	70	77.77	II
3.	Remunerative prices are not received	65	72.22	III
4.	High price fluctuation	58	64.44	IV
5.	Middle man malpractices take place	40	44.44	V

Fig. 1. Production constraints

Fig. 2. Marketing constraints

Suggestions made by chilli growers in Production and Marketing of chilli:

The result indicated that, 84.44 per cent farmers suggest that to take demonstrations on nursery management followed by provide inputs at right time i.e. 74.44 per cent, provide subsidies on fertilizers and pesticides i.e. 65.55 per cent, decrease wage rate of labour i.e. 50 per cent, develop harvesting equipment i.e. 33.33 per cent. (Table 2).

Suggestions related to marketing given by chilli farmers are, provide

market information

i.e. 66.66 per cent, followed by decrease transportation cost i.e. 60 per cent, provide remunerative prices i.e. 55.55 per cent, control price fluctuation i.e. 50 per cent, and control malpractices in marketing i.e. 40 per cent. (Table 2).

Table 2. Suggestion given by chilli growers:

Sr. no.	Production and Marketing Suggestions	N=90	Percent	Rank
Production suggestions				
1.	Take demonstration on Nursery raising	76	84.44	I
2.	Provide inputs at righttime	67	74.44	II
3.	Provide subsidies on fertilizers and pesticides	59	65.55	III
4.	Decrease wage rate of labour	45	50	IV
5.	Develop harvesting equipment	30	33.33	V
Marketing suggestions				
1.	Provide market information	60	66.66	I
2.	Decrease transportation cost	54	60	II
3.	Provide remunerative prices	50	55.55	III
4.	Control price fluctuation	45	50	IV
5.	Control malpractices in marketing	36	40	V

Fig. 3. Production suggestions

Fig. 4. Marketing suggestions

Conclusion:

constraints during chilli cultivation faced by farmers are lack of knowledge of nursery management, unavailability of inputs at right time, high cost of fertilizer, etc.

Farmers suggest that to take demonstrations on nursery management, provide inputs at right time, provide subsidies on fertilizers and pesticides, etc.

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